

INTRODUCING AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES INTO AN UNERGRADUATE ENGINEERING COURSE

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) are of great interest for the automotive industry and are expected to revolutionize mobility and public transportation. The university can contribute to the design and development of autonomous vehicles both in the field of teaching and in research and technology transfer. In this paper, it is described how this topic is introduced in an undergraduate engineering course, "Implementation of Automatic Control Systems (IACS)". The IACS course is based on project based learning (PBL) and learning by doing methodologies. Several practical examples that correspond to real automatic systems are discussed throughout the course and one of them, a low-cost AV to which a Raspberry pi has been adapted, forms the basis for a final project of the course. The control algorithms are developed on MATLAB/SIMULINK and are sent to the Raspberry through a wireless communication network. The control objective of the system is the automatic guidance of the vehicle through a single lane indoor closed circuit, the detection and identification of different traffic signals and the automatic response to these signals. Students check the behavior of the vehicle and proceed to make improvements. Based on the assessment of the students and the robustness of the autonomous vehicles, it is time to consolidate this type of project within the course. Students that want to get deeper into the matter have the opportunity to do a final degree project related with the AV.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Autonomous vehicles

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) are expected to revolutionize mobility and public transportation [1]. There are different types of autonomous vehicles for research and academic purposes. A system classification is required. The most system classification is the one proposed by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) [2]. In this classification there are five levels of automation: from low levels related to human drivers assistance to high levels are related to high automation or fully automation (the autonomous vehicle has the functionality of fault tolerant hardware).

The context of this classification is operate an AV in on-road traffic and developing dynamic driving tasks. The driving automated systems is capable of guiding the AV throughout complete trip, interacting with other AV, solving contingencies, minimizing risk, diverse traffic and weather conditions.

In this paper autonomous vehicles are related to low cost autonomous vehicles with the flexibility to incorporate control electronics, communications with the environment and scalable functionality to generate a wide range of experimental tasks. In a first approach the context of use is in laboratory conditions. The dynamic driving tasks of the SAE must be adapted in this scenario. The main objective is the design and

development of a robust AV and proof that this AV can perform dynamic driving tasks with high effectiveness.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Academic aspects

In the university industrial bachelor degrees of the Barcelona East School of Engineering (EEBE) on the Diagonal-Besòs Campus of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), authors develop the course “Implementation of Automatic Control Systems (IACS)”. This course is an elective course in the last semester of the industrial degrees with 6 European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS).

This course applies the control theory in the development of electronic prototypes and using tools and devices as MATLAB and Raspbeberry pi.

It is an interdisciplinary course since students come from all areas of engineering that are taught in the teaching center (mainly industrial electronics and automatic control, electrical and mechanical engineers). The prerequisites of electronics, programming and linear control theory that are necessary for student success are provided in previous core courses. Good skills in team work are required for the design, development, programming and evaluation of autonomous vehicles prototypes. The course is also available to Erasmus / Exchange students that can have different backgrounds.

The appearance of failures, unexpected vehicle behavior, battery performance, performance of programmed algorithms, require the group to show its ability to resolve contingencies and obtain good vehicle performance.

Authors are driving too final degree projects with the aim to develop first autonomous prototypes with help of the maintenance staff. With the idea of building scalable systems in mind, the student's training is focused on recommending that they first take the course and secondly that they can develop the final degree project.

For the development of fully AV, more capabilities are required. In this sense, the approach presented in this paper should be extended to engineering master's courses and research activities. The authors are developing active work in the development of fault tolerant and safety AV and can provide feedback. The research is developed in a research laboratory and there is a relationship with the academic laboratory commented in this paper.

2.2 Laboratory Practices

The IACS course is based on PBL [3] and learning by doing [4] methodologies. Several practical examples that correspond to real systems are discussed throughout the course and one of them, an AV, forms the basis for a final project. There is a student teaching guide for every practical example with the description of the steps to follow to success in the implementation of an automatic control in a real system (modeling, identification, design, implementation and assessment of the performance) and a description of the results that the student should obtain.

In particular, in the AV example, the implementation of a simple driving automated system in an adapted Van vehicle (shown in Figure 1) is proposed. The vehicle is equipped with a Raspberry Pi 3 B board, a servomotor (steering angle), a DC motor (forward and reverse speed of the vehicle) and a camera. The power supply of the module consist of 5 AA rechargeable batteries and a voltage regulator of 5 Volts. The total cost of the components of the adapted Van vehicle is around 200€.

Fig. 1. Van vehicle adapted with Raspberry Pi 3 B+.

The system is presented as a particular automatic control system composed by the different elements: plant (Van), controller (Raspberry board), actuators (motors) and sensor (Camera). And the control objective is defined as the automatic guidance of the vehicle through the single lane closed indoor circuit depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Single lane closed circuit in the Automation and Industrial Robotics Lab. of the EEBE

The AV guided practice consist in three different steps:

- connecting the vehicle with MATLAB/Simulink through a wireless communication network WIFI conection (router WLAN connected in the Cisco Switch of the laboratory) in such a way it is possible to process the images captured by the camera and control the steering angle and speed of the vehicle.
- how to extract the bounds of the circuit lane (in green color) from the images of the camera.
- how to use the information extracted from the circuit lane bounds to try to align the vehicle with the lane of the circuit.

For this last step, the filtered image that contains the bounds of the lanes is binarized and the centroid of the image is computed (Figure 3). When the vehicle is completely aligned with the lane, the centroid will be aligned with the vertical axis of the image. Therefore, the angle of the centroid with the vertical axis is used as the controlled variable in a close loop system where the controlled variable is the direction of the vehicle and the control objective is to maintain as close as possible the controlled variable to zero (vehicle aligned with the lane).

Fig. 3. Raw and binarized images with centroid and angle deviation δ computations.

In this control system there is another variable that has an important role in the performance of the system, the speed of the vehicle. In this first approximation of the automatic guidance it is considered to be constant. Finally, students are encouraged to detect the limitations of this first approximation of the automatic guidance of the vehicle and the final project of the course is proposed as the implementation of a new (and original) solution. This solution should be robust, reliable, stable and should include other capabilities as the detection and identification of different traffic signals and the automatic response to these signals.

2.3 Project development.

When defining the course content, professors discussed about the software to be used in the laboratories. As all students of EEBE school and most of Erasmus students have used MATLAB program in previous courses and some of them even have used Simulink, the election was clear. In addition, the interface of this software makes programming and learning easy and it is relatively easy to implement complex systems as the one depicted in Figure 4 that implements a possible solution to the AV system.

Fig. 4. Blocs of Simulink circuit that implements AV solution

Red boxes in Figure 4 show how is possible to develop scalable functionality using Simulink (lane detection phase, vehicle control phase, etc.).

To develop the project, the students work in groups of two or three and they have 12 hours of experimental sessions to carry out all the work. The professor discuss with the student team and helps to identify the correct solutions but the final solution and the features to be improved are completely proposed and developed by the students. In the last lab session, each student team presents a summary of the project as well as a demonstration of how the AV system works. After this presentation, professors ask some questions in order to clarify possible confusing points and to assess that all the members of the team group know in deep the final design. The evaluation of the final project is done considering the oral exam and the report of the project. This final evaluation of the overall project counts for 40% of the final mark of the course.

2.4 Final degree project.

Students that want to get deeper into the matter have the opportunity to do a final degree project related with the topic improving the vehicle used in the IACS course and using more professional programming enviroments as the Robot Operating System (ROS). ROS requires lower-level concepts and a steeper learning curve than MATLAB/Simulink enviroment but allows the use of powerful vision libraries as OpenCV [5] and the implementation of advanced artificial intelligence algorithms for the control of the AV as in current professional solutions [6][7].

Figure 5 shows the graph diagram that implements a possible solution to the AV system: From the initial nodes *raspicam_node* and *controller* that allow the capture of images and the implementation of manual/automatic mode selection respectively. To the final node *car_control* that implements the autonomous control considering the environment information obtained from the image processing steps and the controller state. This solution was proposed in a final degree project [8].

Fig. 5. ROS graph diagram showing nodes and topics to control the AV.

Taking into account the students' experience and feedback, new and more complex solutions usually require modifications not only in the programming but also in the hardware setup as for example the use of more powerful Boards that can require an enhanced power supply. For example, ROS software requires at least Raspberry Pi 4 B board that increases the current consumption. Therefore, the new AV requires a more complex power supply unit. In [8] a lithium polymer battery (LIPO) was selected as a suitable solution instead of the original AA rechargeable batteries solution as it is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Van vehicle adapted with Raspberry Pi 4 B.

3 RESULTS

At the end of every quarter, an anonymous survey is conducted by the UPC to obtain feedback from the students of the different courses. In particular, two questions are asked: “1. The contents of the course seemed interesting to me” and “2. Overall, I am satisfied with the course”. Both questions are scored from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) and in the case of IACS course the students have graded an average score of 4.14 and 4.43 to the first and second questions respectively. That is a score 0.3 and 0.9 points above the score obtained in average for all the courses offered by the UPC. In addition, more than a half of the students that take the IACS course are interested in doing the final degree project related with the topics of the course. Regarding academic results, 13% of the students have satisfactory results [5,7), 40% very good results [7-9) and 40% very good results. Finally, only 7% of students have not satisfactory results [0,5) because they have problems to attend to the experimental sessions.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This article presents an example of how Autonomous Vehicles have been included in an undergraduated engineering course in a motivating way, in particular, in an elective course of the industrial bachelor degrees of the Barcelona East School of Engineering at UPC. AV have been introduced first in an introductory guided practical lab and after following learning by doing methodology to solve a real-world problem. Learning by doing is used to increase students' interest and at the same time help them to acquire and apply new knowledge in a problem-solving context. Student surveys and assessment results confirm the student's great interest and success in the course.

As future lines, the authors want to introduce AV in other courses. In particular, in an advanced control elective course in the last semester of the Bachelor's degree in Industrial Electronics and Automatic Control Engineering. Previous background of students in automatic control, programming and electronics will be deeper than the one of average students in IACS course. This circumstance will allow the use of ROS environment in the implementation of AV algorithms. However, a key point to obtain satisfactory results will be the design of educational modules to simplify learning about this environment. Because ROS is not in the curricula of previous courses of this Bachelor degree.

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